

Research Paper

A quasi-two-stage *trans*-critical CO₂ heat pump with in-cycle thermal storage for performance enhancement

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ABSTRACT

To decarbonise the heating sector, there is a strong demand for environmentally friendly and cost-effective heating technologies. Trans-critical CO₂ heat pumps offer a sustainable alternative to traditional vapor compression cycles that rely on environmentally harmful synthetic refrigerants. However, a significant challenge within *trans*-critical CO₂ heat pumps is their high throttling loss during expansion, leading to substantial flash gas production and subsequently higher recompression power consumption. In this paper, we apply our Flexible Heat Pump cycle concept to *trans*-critical CO₂ heat pumps to address this issue. A thermal storage unit is introduced into a traditional *trans*-critical CO₂ heat pump cycle to recover heat from the hot super-critical CO₂ leaving the gas cooler during charging mode. Once it is fully charged, the stored heat is then used as a temporary heat source for the heat pump's operation during the discharging mode. Since the recovered heat has a higher temperature than ambient. The resultant flexible *trans*-critical CO₂ heat pump (FlexiCO₂-HP) reduces throttling losses and the compressor's power consumption, leading to a higher average COP (Coefficient of Performance). The obtained results of the FlexiCO₂-HP are compared against a single-stage *trans*-critical CO₂ heat pump. For gas cooler temperatures ranging from 35 °C to 60 °C and across various discharge pressures, its COP is potentially 10 % to 40 % higher than the standard cycle under ideal conditions. In addition, the proposed system demonstrates a lower optimal gas cooler pressure across different gas cooler temperatures. Furthermore, this study compares the FlexiCO₂-HP with other *trans*-critical CO₂ systems, including those with expansion work recovery and two-stage configurations. The results demonstrate that the FlexiCO₂-HP offers improvements in COP for most conditions, though not all. It has the potential to achieve a comparable COP when compared with ejector-based and expander-based heat pumps or two-stage systems, but it is much simpler in design without introducing an extra expander or compressor.

1. Introduction

Most energy is converted into heat for use in home and industrial settings. As most countries continue to burn fossil fuels for heat supply, the heating sector is one key emitter of greenhouse. Therefore, swift action is required, including a switch to low carbon heating solutions such as heat pumps. The International Energy Agency (IEA) estimates that 174.9 million heat pumps have been installed worldwide by 2020, with a target of 600 million units by 2030. In the United Kingdom, the government plans to install 600,000 heat pumps annually by 2028. However, the uptake of heat pump in the UK is currently low with only 72,000 installed in 2022. Hence, it is essential to speed up the installation of various heat pump technologies to achieve the government's heat decarbonisation target.

Most buildings in the United Kingdom utilise boilers for heating, which operate at temperatures around 65 °C, whereas heat pumps function at temperatures about 55 °C. At this temperature, the radiators need be much larger, resulting in substantial retrofitting costs. By increasing the temperature of single-stage heat pumps, the coefficient of performance (COP) declines and, as a result, the power consumption rises, making high-temperature heat pumps less efficient. The reason for this is that when the condenser temperature increases, the throttling loss also increases. Two-stage heat pumps working at higher temperatures therefore are more desirable due to their greater COP. However, the use of two or more compressors in two-stage heat pumps raises the cost and system complexity.

Most heat pumps use synthetic refrigerants with a high global warming potential (GWP). For instance, R134a is a typical refrigerant

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that is utilised in heat pump systems. Although it does not deplete the ozone layer, its GWP is 1430, namely 1430 times greater than that of CO₂ [1]. R410A, another typical common refrigerant, has a GWP 2,000 [2]. Hence, refrigerant leaks from heat pumps and refrigerators exacerbates the emission problem [3]. CO₂ has a negligible GWP (GWP = 1 and ODP = 0) and a very cheap because it is a by-product of industrial production, which is why it was included in the Kyoto Protocol [4,5]. Ammonia is also a very efficient natural refrigerant, but because it is toxic and flammable, it cannot be utilized in residential applications. In contrast, CO₂ is non-explosive, non-toxic, and non-corrosive. From an environmental, financial, and safety standpoint, CO₂ is a suitable alternative natural refrigerant, as it causes no ozone depletion (ODP) and has a small global warming potential (GWP), and very low cost. As a result, CO₂ heat pumps operating under *trans*-critical conditions can serve as a viable alternative to vapour compression cycles employing synthetic refrigerants.

Lorentzen was one of the first researchers to suggest using CO₂ as a refrigerant in a vapor compression system [6,7]. Compression, heat rejection via the gas cooler, expansion, and heat absorption via the evaporator are the four processes that make up a *trans*-critical heat pump. The fundamental disadvantage of *trans*-critical CO₂ cycles is the significant throttle loss as the refrigerant passes through throttling device. As a result, the COP of *trans*-critical CO₂ heat pump is lower than that of traditional sub-critical vapour compression systems with refrigerants such as CFCs and HFCs.

Various technologies, such as ejectors, expanders, internal subcooling heat exchangers, and two-stage systems, have been developed to recover energy during the expansion process, and thus to reduce the throttling loss. By replacing the throttle valve with a work-generating expander, energy can be recovered from the refrigerant to produce power during expansion process [8–10]. To effectively recover the throttling loss, the expander's efficiency must be high [11]. For all expanders, internal and external leakages as well as friction loss represents a significant challenge that drastically reduces their efficiency (depending on the size of the leakage gap) [12–16]. On the other hand, the design of a two-phase expander operating in the liquid–vapor region is technically complex and economically undesirable [13,16]. In addition to expanders, ejectors have also been considered for power recovery during expansion process, which uses the high-pressure refrigerant as the motive stream for the ejector jet to extract work from the CO₂ refrigerant and assist in driving the compressor through the expansion process [17]. The COP of *trans*-critical heat pumps with ejector is extremely sensitive to ejector efficiency, and the cycle can reach its maximum COP only if the ejector efficiency is incredibly high, which is not attainable in practice and is typically less than 20 % [18–21]. Numerous studies suggest that integrating an internal heat exchanger (IHX) as a sub-cooler can improve the energy performance of the cycle, depending on the type of refrigerant used, and that a higher vapor heat capacity can raise the COP [22].

Wang et al. [23] analysed the heating performance of a CO₂ *trans*-critical heat pump system with a sub-cooler. The effect of subcooling temperature has been demonstrated and a maximum heating COP of 3.04 was obtained at an optimal discharge pressure of 10.025 MPa with an ambient temperature of 5 °C. Using a fixed CO₂ gas cooler outlet temperature at 35 °C, an optimum heating COP of 2.63 was achieved at a lower pressure of 9.4 MPa. In a study by Yang et al. [24] on a *trans*-critical CO₂ heat pump system with a thermoelectric sub-cooler, the optimal performance was achieved with a subcooling degree of 11 °C and a gas cooler pressure and temperature of 8.0 MPa and 35 °C. Under these conditions, the system's heating COP is increased by 13.3 %.

However, Domanski and Didion pointed out that apart from the fact that the most influential parameter is the vapor heat capacity, other parameters such as operating conditions, latent heat and coefficient of thermal expansion can be effective in the system performance [22]. It must be considered that the influence of internal heat exchange on the CO₂ *trans*-critical cycle is marginal, and in the high temperature lift

compressor, discharge temperature will be high enough to damage the lubricant [25]. In order to achieve a greater COP and a lower optimum discharge pressure, the heat transfer area (or length of HX) of IHX must be increased, resulting in an increase in cost. Moreover, when IHX length increases, the heating capacity of the cycle tends to decrease [26]. Therefore, it is necessary to determine whether the increase in COP is sufficient to justify the growth in the system's capital cost (due to the increase of IHX length). Utilizing the aforementioned technologies can increase the COP, but they are technically highly difficult and commercially unappealing. Therefore, innovation is essential to create a cost-effective technique for enhancing the COP of *trans*-critical CO₂ heat pump technology. Mancinelli et al. [27] presented a CO₂ *trans*-critical heat pump design for water heating that increases the overall COP by integrating thermal energy storage (TES) outside the heat pump cycle, offering a cost-effective method for improving cycle efficiency comparable to ejector-expansion systems or double compression.

The author's newly developed flexible heat pump cycle introduces a heat storage unit into the heat pump cycle to recover, store, and reuse some of the sensible heat carried by the hot refrigerant exiting the condenser. This provides a new alternative approach to decrease the inefficiencies caused by significant throttling losses [28]. So far, the COP enhancement of the flexible heat pump over the single-stage heat pump has been demonstrated in a sub-critical condition. This concept has theoretically demonstrated a potential reduction in power consumption by 20 % with a fixed condenser temperature of 65 °C when the evaporation temperature is 0 °C.

In this paper, we propose to apply the flexible heat pump concept to *trans*-critical CO₂ cycles to address the issue of very high throttling losses, leading to a *trans*-critical flexible CO₂ heat pump cycle, which is denoted as 'FlexiCO₂-HP' thereafter. The resultant FlexiCO₂-HP has been modelled theoretically and analysed numerically. The obtained results are compared with traditional single-stage CO₂ *trans*-critical heat pumps to demonstrate its capability for COP improvement. Furthermore, we compare its performance to heat pumps with expanders and ejectors, as well as different two-stage heat pumps. These comparisons are critical for understanding the FlexiCO₂-HP's advantages, particularly its efficiency enhancement and flexibility.

2. Thermodynamic models

2.1. Standard *trans*-critical heat pump

The standard single-stage *trans*-critical heat pump along with the proposed FlexiCO₂-HP and the thermodynamic processes of these cycles in a p-h diagram are shown in Fig. 1. a – Fig. 1. f.

There are four main components in a *trans*-critical standard heat pump cycle including a compressor, a gas cooler, an expansion device, and an evaporator. The way the cycle works has been depicted in Fig. 1. a, the CO₂ saturated vapor enters the compressor with a pressure of P_1 , then it compresses to a higher pressure and temperature (point 2). The high pressure and temperature refrigerant release the heat to the external loop (e.g., water or air). As a result, the outlet flow from the compressor is cool down to T_3 at constant pressure of P_2 and then enters the expansion valve and its pressure abruptly decreases to P_4 . The heat removed from the cold air (in the case or air source heat pump) is absorbed by the liquid–vapor refrigerant that is passing through the evaporator and it converts to the saturated vapor at point 1 and then returns to the compressor for circulation. The thermodynamics of the *trans*-critical CO₂ standard HP is shown in Fig. 1. b which demonstrates the change in pressure and enthalpy that occurs during the cycle.

In simulation of the *trans*-critical heat pump cycle, each of the component is considered as a control volume. Using the energy and mass balance in each component the governing equations are obtained. As it can be seen in Fig. 1. b the gas cooler duty (\dot{Q}_{GS}) is calculated as:

$$\dot{Q}_{GS} = \dot{m}_s(h_{II} - h_{III}) \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1. CO₂ Standard *trans*-critical HP and flexible CO₂ *trans*-critical HP (FlexiCO₂-HP) and their p-h diagrams: (a) standard *trans*-critical HP; (b) p-h diagram standard HP (c) Charging mode of the FlexiCO₂-HP; (d) Charging mode p-h diagram; (e) Discharging mode of the FlexiCO₂-HP; (f) Discharging mode p-h diagram. Abbreviations – C: Compressor, G: Gas cooler, EX: Expansion valve, TES: Thermal energy storage, E: Evaporator, F: Four-way valve, v: Three-way valve.

where \dot{m}_s is the mass flow rate of CO₂ refrigerant, h is the specific enthalpy, subscript “S” presents the standard *trans*-critical CO₂ HP cycle and subscript G is represented for the gas cooler.

The heat transfer rate ($\dot{Q}_{E,S}$) of the evaporator is expressed as:

$$\dot{Q}_{E,S} = \dot{m}_s(h_I - h_{IV}) \quad (2)$$

where subscript E represents the evaporator.

Consumption power by the compressor ($\dot{W}_{C,S}$) is defined as:

$$\dot{W}_{C,S} = \dot{m}_s(h_{II} - h_I) \quad (3)$$

here subscripts I to IV represent the numbering of the state points shown in Fig. 1. a and Fig. 1. b.

Consequently, the COP in the standard *trans*-critical CO₂ HP is calculated as:

$$COP_S = \frac{\dot{Q}_{G,S}}{\dot{W}_{C,S}} \quad (4)$$

2.2. The flexible *trans*-critical CO₂ heat pump (FlexiCO₂-HP) cycle

In a standard *trans*-critical CO₂ cycle as shown in Fig. 1. a and Fig. 1. b, high temperature and pressure CO₂ refrigerant leaves the gas-cooler and then it throttled via an expansion valve to reach the evaporator temperature and pressure. As a result, whatever energy that was used to increase the pressure of the CO₂ refrigerant is dissipated as it expands to the lower pressure region. In the proposed FlexiCO₂-HP, as illustrated in Fig. 1c, carbon dioxide at high pressure undergoes further cooling (subcooling) within the TES unit. This process effectively recovers a portion of the sensible heat from the hot CO₂ exiting the gas cooler. The corresponding p-h diagram shown in Fig. 1d. demonstrates the heat recovery phase during the charging mode of the cycle.

The heat recovered by the TES can be released when the TES acts as a temporary evaporator in the discharging mode, as shown in Fig. 1e. This

dual functionality allows the FlexiCO₂-HP to operate in various modes—charging and discharging—depending on the system’s thermal needs. A four-way valve facilitates the mode transition, directing the working fluid from the gas cooler to the TES, expansion valve, and evaporator during the charging operation, and from the gas cooler to the expansion valve and TES during the discharging operation.

This heat recovery and storage enhance the cycle’s efficiency by enabling it to store and later reuse heat that would otherwise be wasted. In the discharging mode, the TES serves as a temporary evaporator, operating at a temperature higher than the ambient, which is a significant improvement over traditional *trans*-critical heat pump systems where the evaporator typically operates at ambient temperature. This higher operating temperature during the discharging phase can improve the heat pump’s COP and efficiency. Thermodynamically speaking, the proposed FlexiCO₂-HP enables a quasi-two-stage operation using only one compressor.

To compare the standard *trans*-critical heat pump cycle and FlexiCO₂-HP under the same conditions, the evaporator temperature is set at 0 °C for both systems. In the FlexiCO₂-HP, the lower bound of TES temperature is 0 °C and the upper bound of TES temperature is slightly below the CO₂ critical temperature because the low-pressure side of the cycle operates in the subcritical condition (see Fig. 1f).

To simplify the simulation, the assumptions considered in the current study are presented below:

- Pressure loss is neglected in the heat exchangers.
- The pressure drops in the connecting pipelines used in the cycle to transfer the refrigerant between different equipment are neglected.
- Heat losses in the connecting pipelines are neglected.
- Heat transfer in the heat exchangers is assumed to be isothermal.
- Compressors are isentropic and have 100 % efficiency.
- The enthalpy of the refrigerant will remain constant after passing through the expansion valve.

- The heat duty of the gas cooler is assumed to be constant for all studied cases (i.e. 4 kW).
- The system is simulated under steady state conditions.

It should be noted that the equations of the FlexiCO₂-HP are similar to those in the FlexiCO₂-HP cycle, as described in our previous article [28]. In that work, we also provided a detailed analysis of both latent and sensible heat storage systems, along with the relevant calculations. For clarity and to avoid repetition, the current paper focuses on key equations related to the storage tank, but further details regarding the storage system can be found in the previous publication [28].

The total heat charged to the heat storage can be calculated as follows [28]:

$$Q_{charge} = \dot{m}_r (h_3 - h_4) \Delta t_{charge} \quad (5)$$

where \dot{m}_r , h_3 and h_4 are independent of time.

The power consumption of the compressor is calculated as follows:

$$\dot{W}_C = \dot{m}_r (h_2 - h_1) \quad (6)$$

As a result, the heat pump's COP can be expressed as

$$COP_{charge} = \frac{\dot{Q}_G}{\dot{W}_C} = \frac{h_2 - h_3}{h_2 - h_1} \quad (7)$$

During the discharge, the heat capacity of the gas cooler can be stated as

$$\dot{Q}_{G'} = \dot{m}_r (h_2' - h_3') \quad (8)$$

We assume that $\dot{Q}_{G'} = \dot{Q}_G$, where we have:

$$\dot{Q}_G = \dot{m}_r (h_2 - h_3) \quad (9)$$

In the discharging mode, the heat storage acts as a temporary evaporator, and the discharge rate is calculated as:

$$\dot{Q}_{discharge} = \dot{m}_r (h_{1'} - h_{5'}) \quad (10)$$

Since \dot{m}_r , $h_{1'}$, and $h_{5'}$ remain unchanged during discharging mode, the total heat discharged by the heat storage can be estimated using:

$$Q_{discharge} = \dot{m}_r (h_{1'} - h_{5'}) \Delta t_{discharge} \quad (11)$$

Similarly, the compressor power is calculated as:

$$\dot{W}_{C'} = \dot{m}_r (h_{2'} - h_{1'}) \quad (12)$$

and the total work of compressor during discharging is presented as:

$$W_{C'} = \dot{m}_r (h_{2'} - h_{1'}) \Delta t_{discharge} \quad (13)$$

Hence, the system's COP during the discharge mode can be presented as

$$COP_{discharge} = \frac{Q_{G'}}{W_{C'}} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{G'}}{\dot{W}_{C'}} = \frac{h_{2'} - h_{3'}}{h_{2'} - h_{1'}} \quad (14)$$

For equilibrium, the heat released during discharge should match the heat absorbed during charge, assuming the heat storage achieves a 100 % round-trip efficiency, leading to the following relationship:

$$\dot{Q}_{discharge} \Delta t_{discharge} = \dot{Q}_{charge} \Delta t_{charge} \quad (15)$$

The overall heat output from the heat pump across a full charging/discharging cycle is determined by:

$$Q_{total} = \dot{Q}_G \Delta t_{charge} + \dot{Q}_{G'} \Delta t_{discharge} = \dot{Q}_G (\Delta t_{charge} + \Delta t_{discharge}) \quad (16)$$

Total compressor work can be calculated as:

$$W_{total} = \dot{W}_C \Delta t_{charge} + \dot{W}_{C'} \Delta t_{discharge} \quad (17)$$

Consequently, the average COP for the FlexiCO₂-HP over a complete charging/discharging cycle can be computed as:

$$COP_{avg} = \frac{Q_{total}}{W_{total}} = \frac{\dot{Q}_G (\Delta t_{charge} + \Delta t_{discharge})}{\dot{W}_C \Delta t_{charge} + \dot{W}_{C'} \Delta t_{discharge}} \quad (18)$$

To evaluate the performance enhancements, we define the parameter α , which represents the COP improvement offered by the FlexiCO₂-HP over the baseline as follows:

$$\alpha = \frac{COP_{avg} - COP_S}{COP_S} \times 100\% \quad (19)$$

where COP_S refers to the coefficient of performance for the baseline model, which is a single-stage *trans*-critical CO₂ heat pump as shown in Eq. (4).

The thermodynamic properties in this study were evaluated using REFPROP V9.0. The inlet state of the compressor is assumed to be saturated vapor, with the evaporator temperature set at 0 °C. This allows for the calculation of other thermodynamic properties, such as enthalpy and entropy. For the gas cooler, the temperature is considered a given parameter, ranging between 35 °C and 60 °C, depending on the optimal gas cooler pressure in the system. Additionally, the heat production from the gas cooler is assumed to be 4 kW.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. *Trans*-critical flexible CO₂ heat pump (FlexiCO₂-HP)

When using sub-critical heat pumps, the COP is limited by the high-temperature side. In contrast, in the *trans*-critical CO₂ cycle the high-pressure side operates independently of temperature, making it necessary to control pressure in order to achieve the optimal COP and minimize power consumption. As a result, in a standard *trans*-critical heat pump, achieving optimal results requires strict regulation of the gas cooler pressure within a specific range. The 3D plot in Fig. 2 provides a comprehensive visualization of the COP for the FlexiCO₂-HP. It distinctly illustrates how the COP_{avg} is affected by the interplay of the thermal energy storage (TES) tank temperature (T_{TES}) and the gas cooler pressure (P_{gas}), while maintaining a constant outlet gas cooler temperature (T_{TES}) at 50 °C and evaporator temperature of 0 °C.

A noteworthy observation from the plot is the significant role of T_{TES} in conjunction with P_{gas} to influence the COP_{avg} . Unlike standard *trans*-

Fig. 2. The COP of the FlexibleCO₂-HP at varying gas cooler pressures and storage tank temperatures. The temperature of the gas cooler and evaporator are set at a constant value of 50 °C and 0 °C, respectively.

critical CO₂ heat pump systems where the COP primarily fluctuates with pressure changes, the FlexiCO₂-HP cycle adds an extra layer of complexity and control through T_{TES} . This variable modulation presents an opportunity to fine-tune the system for enhanced efficiency. As T_{TES} increases, we observe a corresponding rise in COP_{avg} until it reaches the maximum, beyond which the COP_{avg} starts to descend. Similarly, the COP_{avg} initially increases with P_{gas} before it hits a peak and subsequently decreases with further elevations in pressure suggesting that there is an ideal range of T_{TES} and P_{gas} values that could be targeted for maximum operational COP.

The 2D contour plot shown in Fig. 3a is a top-down view of the previously discussed 3D surface in Fig. 2, depicting the relationship between the T_{TES} , P_{gas} , and the COP_{avg} of the FlexiCO₂-HP, with a constant outlet gas cooler temperature set at 50 °C. The contour plot clearly shows where the COP_{avg} is highest, with warmer colors marking the best combination of P_{gas} and T_{TES} for maximum efficiency. For the gas-cooler temperature of 50 °C, the optimal P_{gas} is observed to be within the lower-range of the scale, around 11.5 to 13.5 MPa. Similarly, the optimal T_{TES} for the highest COP_{avg} is found to be between 20 °C and 28 °C. Outside of these optimal ranges, the COP_{avg} is shown to decrease in a gradient,

becoming lower as the conditions move away from this central peak.

As the thermal energy storage tank temperature decreases, the heat captured during the charging mode increases, potentially enhancing the average COP of the FlexiCO₂-HP. However, a lower temperature on the low-pressure side during the discharging mode may lead to a decrease in average COP. Thus, these two effects compete with each other, resulting in an optimal TES temperature for each set of conditions at the gas cooler. With a reduction in gas cooler temperature from 50 °C to 40 °C, the peak COP of the FlexiCO₂-HP shifts towards a higher TES temperatures and lower gas cooler pressures as shown in Fig. 3b.

At the TES's optimal temperature, lowering the gas cooler temperature leads to an increase in the specific heat rejected during both charging and discharging modes of the FlexiCO₂-HP. As a result, when the gas cooler's duty is maintained at 4 kW, the mass flow rate decreases during both the charging and discharging modes. Simultaneously, there is a decline in the power requirement for the compressor for both cycles due to the decrease in the mass flow rate, which, in turn, enhances the COP of charging and discharging modes. Conversely, a reduction in the gas cooler temperature reduces the quantity of heat stored in the TES, consequently shortening the discharging mode's duration and decreasing the average COP of the FlexiCO₂-HP cycle. To achieve a balance and find the maximum COP, it is crucial to carefully adjust the pressure of the gas cooler. As a result, to achieve a higher COP at a lower gas cooler temperature, the gas cooler pressure must be reduced in the optimal temperature of TES as shown in Fig. 3b.

So far, we have applied the flexible heat pump's concept to the *trans*-critical condition using CO₂ as the refrigerant. Moving forward, we compare the COP of the FlexiCO₂-HP to the standard *trans*-critical CO₂ heat pump.

3.2. Comparison of the FlexiCO₂-HP and single-stage *trans*-critical CO₂ heat pump

The results depicted in Fig. 4 demonstrates the relation of the COP improvement (α), pressure and temperature of the gas cooler and TES temperature. The curves in the graph depict several temperature ranges for the gas cooler, ranging from 35 °C to 60 °C. T_{gas} has a significant impact on α , as evidenced by the distinct patterns observed at each temperature level.

The optimum temperature of the heat storage tank, T_{TES} , is a significant aspect of this study and we need to determine the best T_{TES} for each combination of gas cooler temperature and pressure. The graph shows the Optimal T_{TES} corresponding to various gas cooler conditions that leads to the higher COP. As a result, the data displayed at the optimal TES temperatures, leading us to represent them in a 3D line curves rather than a surface for a clearer visualization (see Fig. 4. a). Occurrence of peaks at different values of T_{gas} is an important observation from the plot. This suggests that for each specific gas cooler temperature, there is an optimal gas cooler pressure which, combined with the corresponding optimal T_{TES} , leads to the maximum α .

The 3D graph has been represented in 2D views from different perspectives, including the x-z and x-y planes, to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the results (See Fig. 4. b and 4. c). The optimal TES temperatures are shown in Fig. 4. b at different gas cooler pressures, and Fig. 4. c shows the corresponding optimal α . It is evident from the figure that the optimal gas cooler pressure for maximizing α rises with an increase in the gas cooler temperature in optimal TES temperatures.

In addition, to achieve the highest α , it is necessary to identify both the optimal TES temperature and the optimal gas cooler pressure at a specific gas cooler temperature.

To better comprehend the results, we combined the results from Fig. 4. c and b in Fig. 5, which illustrate the effect of gas cooler pressure on COP improvement at various TES temperatures for the gas cooler temperature of 50 °C. The maximum value of α that can be achieved with a gas cooler operating at 50 °C is 17.50 %. This occurs when the gas

Fig. 3. Contour plot representing the average COP as a function of the gas cooler pressure and thermal energy storage (TES) temperature (in °C) at a fixed gas cooler temperature of (a). 50 °C and (b). 40 °C. The colour gradient illustrates the average COP values, with the warmer colours indicating higher value.

Fig. 4. (a) Effects of gas-cooler temperature on the optimal COP improvement (α) in its associated optimal PCM temperature at different gas-cooler pressures; (b) x-z view; (c) x-y view.

Fig. 5. Relationship between the gas cooler pressure and the optimal COP improvement (α , shown in %) and optimal thermal energy storage temperature (T_{TES} , shown in $^{\circ}\text{C}$) for a *trans*-critical CO_2 heat pump at a fixed gas cooler temperature of 50°C .

cooler pressure is at 11.05 MPa and the TES performs optimally at a temperature of 22.9°C .

Fig. 6a and 6b present two contour plots of α as a function of the evaporator temperature and the thermal energy storage temperature, under two conditions of gas cooler temperature and pressure.

This figure offers a comprehensive contour map for determining the most advantageous operational parameters for the FlexiCO₂-HP. In this figure, we can observe the crucial interactions between the evaporator temperature, the thermal energy storage temperature, and the resulting α under different gas cooler conditions. Building on this analysis, an example from Fig. 6. a illustrates that at an evaporator temperature of around -20°C , the T_{TES} required to reach the 10 % improvement in COP can be directly read from the contour line that intersects at this T_{Eva} value ($T_{TES} = 2^{\circ}\text{C}$). As T_{Eva} increases towards 0°C , the required T_{TES} to maintain the same level of improvement in COP also increases, demonstrating a clear correlation between T_{Eva} and T_{TES} for optimizing the system's performance. In other words, for an α of 10 %, the plot demonstrates that T_{Eva} must be between -17°C to -6°C .

From this contour graph, we can also find the optimal T_{TES} , at which the α is the maximum in different operational conditions of FlexiCO₂-HP. For example, at a T_{Eva} of 10°C , the maximum α of 6 % is achieved when T_{TES} is approximately 26°C . In Fig. 6a and 6b, it is observed that with an increase in evaporator temperature or a reduction in the lift temperature, the optimal TES temperature increases accordingly.

Fig. 6. Effects of varying parameters on α in a FlexiCO₂-HP cycle: (a) Contour map showing the relationship between T_{eva} and T_{TES} at a gas cooler pressure of 17 MPa and a fixed gas cooler temperature of 50 °C. Lines represent constant α values, demonstrating how α varies with changes in T_{eva} and T_{TES} . (b) Contour map under similar conditions but at a reduced gas cooler pressure of 12.5 MPa, illustrating shifts in the variability of α with adjustments in T_{eva} and T_{TES} at a lower pressure.

3.3. Comparison of FlexiCO₂-HP's performance with different two-stage heat pumps

In our previous research [29], we compared the sub-critical Flexible Heat Pump cycle with various two-stage subcritical heat pump cycles. In this section, similarly, the proposed FlexiCO₂-HP cycle is compared with various *trans*-critical two-stage CO₂ heat pump cycles.

Their cycle layouts and the corresponding p-h diagrams are illustrated in Fig. 7, including: subcooling with partial intercooling (SC&PIC) as shown in Fig. 7a, subcooling with fully intercooling (SC&FIC) as shown in Fig. 7b, flash gas removal with partial inter cooling (FGR&PIC) as shown in Fig. 7c, flash gas removal with fully inter cooling (FGR&FIC) as shown in Fig. 7d, flash gas removal only (FGR) as shown in Fig. 7e, and subcooling only (SC) as shown in Fig. 7f.

Fig. 8 presents a comprehensive comparison of the COP improvement α between the FlexiCO₂-HP cycle and those two-stage *trans*-critical systems. The bar chart illustrates the COP improvements achieved by the FlexiCO₂-HP cycle relative to six different two-stage heat pump configurations, ranging from systems incorporating intercooling (IC), subcooling (SC), flash gas removal (FGR) and to those utilising a combination of these functionalities. In all cases, the optimal intermediate temperatures and gas cooler pressures are obtained for α and its value is compared with the FlexiCO₂-HP at a gas cooler temperature of 50 °C.

Table 1 shows the optimal gas cooler pressures for all the different two-stage cycles along with their optimal intermediate temperatures in the *trans*-critical condition using CO₂. It can be observed that configurations with full subcooling (SC) yield a greater improvement in COP compared to those with flash gas removal (FGR). This is attributed to the slope of the isotherm line in the saturated liquid region, which effectively increases the COP for configurations with subcooling. For instance, the combination of SC with FIC (SC&FIC) demonstrates a higher COP improvement compared to the combination of FGR with FIC (FGR&FIC). Similarly, the SC with PIC (SC&PIC) also shows a more significant COP improvement than its FGR&PIC counterpart. This indicates that fully leveraging subcooling in the cycle can be more effective than flash gas removal for enhancing the heat pump's overall performance in the case of CO₂.

It can also be seen that the FlexiCO₂-HP surpasses all the two-stage layouts in terms of COP improvement, with the exception of the SC&PIC system. However, the SC&PIC improvement margin of 17.75 % is close to the FlexiCO₂-HP's 17.50 %. In addition, both the FlexiCO₂-HP and the SC cycles have the same α value, which is equal to 17.50 %. As a result, the FlexiCO₂-HP is theoretically equivalence with a *trans*-critical

CO₂ two-stage heat pump with a flash tank that acts as a full sub-cooler. This implies that the FlexiCO₂-HP can achieve the same level of performance as the two-stage systems but with fewer equipment, resulting in a significant reduction in the system cost.

In conclusion, the operational complexity and additional costs introduced by expanders and ejectors, which often do not achieve high efficiencies in practical applications, support the adoption of simpler systems like the FlexiCO₂-HP cycle. In addition, by requiring only a single compressor, the FlexiCO₂-HP cycle significantly reduces mechanical complexity compared to conventional two-stage cycles, which typically require two compressors.

This simplification not only eases installation and maintenance but also enhances system reliability and lowers overall costs, establishing the FlexiCO₂-HP cycle as a superior choice in terms of both efficiency and simplicity compared to systems that incorporate ejectors, expanders, or rely on two-stage configurations.

3.4. Comparison of FlexiCO₂-HP's performance with expander HP cycles

It is important to note that the simulations for the FlexiCO₂-HP in Sections 3.1–3.3 assume an ideal compressor efficiency of 100 % for simplicity. These results represent the theoretical maximum COP that both the FlexiCO₂-HP cycle and the two-stage heat pump cycles could achieve under ideal conditions, providing a fair like-for-like comparison. The results have demonstrated that the COP of the FlexiCO₂-HP cycle shows similar improvement to two stage cycles, when single stage heat pump cycle is used as the baseline.

In this section, our research compares the FlexiCO₂-HP with other expansion work recovery methods, such as expanders and ejectors. For a fair and realistic comparison, this section incorporates practical efficiencies for compressors, expanders, and ejectors. The typical efficiency ranges for these devices are estimated based on published experimental studies. Aside from these three components, the other assumptions listed in Section 2.2 remain unchanged. Additionally, the operational parameters are kept consistent across these three system designs.

The efficiency of CO₂ compressor under *trans*-critical conditions is calculated as a function of the pressure ratio (R_p) using the following equation [30,31]:

$$\eta_{comp} = -0.0021(R_p)^2 - 0.0155(R_p) + 0.7325 \quad (20)$$

Based on the results shown in Fig. 9, the compressor efficiency in *trans*-critical conditions is depicted as a function of the gas cooler pressure when the evaporator temperature is 0 °C. This efficiency correlation is

Fig. 7. Different two-stage cycle layouts: (a) Subcooling with partial intercooling (SC&PIC), (b) Subcooling with fully intercooling (SC&FIC), (c) Flash gas removal with partial inter cooling (FGR&PIC), (d) Flash gas removal with fully inter cooling (FGR&FIC), (e) Only flash gas removal (FGR), (f) Only subcooling (SC).

used to ensure a realistic and fair comparison between different heat pump configurations, including the FlexiCO₂-HP and the heat pumps with an expander or an ejector. As a result, this efficiency curve is applied to all configurations to analyse their performance of each system under the same operational conditions.

The reported CO₂ ejector efficiency from experimental studies ranges between 0.2 and 0.4 [32], e.g., the ejector's highest efficiency reaches 0.308 in reference [33], and a maximum efficiency of 0.4 is reported in [34]. Therefore, the ejector efficiency is considered in a range of 0.2 to 0.4 for the analysis in this paper to compare with the FlexiCO₂-HP.

In Fig. 10, the COP of the FlexiCO₂-HP cycle is compared with heat pumps equipped with an ejector. The x-axis represents the gas cooler pressure, and the analysis is conducted at a constant gas cooler temperature of 50 °C and an evaporator temperature of 0 °C. As shown in the Fig. 10, the gas cooler pressure varies between 9 MPa and 17 MPa, and the compressor efficiency changes according to Fig. 9 and Equation (20). For instance, at 9 MPa, the compressor efficiency is approximately 68 %, while at 17 MPa, it drops to around 61 %.

As shown in the Fig. 10, the blue line indicates the COP of the FlexiCO₂-HP. The COP of the FlexiCO₂-HP appears slightly better than the ejector-based heat pump with the ejector efficiency between 20 % and 40 %. However, it is important to note that our results are based on ideal conditions in heat exchangers, such as an ideal TES. Nevertheless, the results shown in Fig. 10 imply that the FlexiCO₂-HP has the potential to achieve a comparable COP to that of the ejector heat pump cycles. The impact of the roundtrip efficiency of the TES on the FlexiCO₂-HP will be discussed in next section.

In a similar way, we can compare the FlexiCO₂-HP with expander heat pump cycles under *trans*-critical conditions. There are not many experimental studies of using expanders in *trans*-critical CO₂ heat pumps. An experimental study reported that a scroll expander reached an isentropic efficiency of 55 % in a CO₂ *trans*-critical heat pump system under optimal operating conditions [35]. Another experimental study tested a two-rolling piston expander in a *trans*-critical CO₂ heat pump system. The results showed that, under varying rotational speeds, the expander efficiency ranged from 28 % to 33 % [36]. Hence, a range between 28 % to 55 % is adopted as the expander efficiency for the

Fig. 8. COP improvement for the FlexiCO₂-HP and various two-stage cycles.

comparison with the FlexiCO₂-HP in this paper.

Fig. 11 compares the COP of the FlexiCO₂-HP when the TES is at 23 °C with that of the expander-based heat pump at different gas cooler pressures, with a fixed gas cooler temperature of 50 °C. As shown in Fig. 11, the FlexiCO₂-HP's maximum COP outperforms the expander heat pump cycle when the expander's efficiency is 28 %. However, the expander heat pump cycle outperforms if the expander's isentropic efficiency is 55 %. The results imply that the FlexiCO₂-HP can achieve a similar COP to expander-based heat pump systems.

3.5. Impact of TES efficiency on the performance of the FlexiCO₂-HP

The proposed FlexiCO₂-HP benefits from the quasi-two-stage operation because its charging mode has the same COP as a standard single stage CO₂ heat pump, while its discharging mode has a higher COP since the stored heat with a temperature than ambient is used as a temporary heat source. Hence, the performance of the thermal energy storage has strong influence on the performance of the FlexiCO₂-HP. In this section, the impact of the roundtrip efficiency of the thermal energy storage has been analysed.

Fig. 12 shows a clear correlation between TES efficiency and COP improvement. At 100 % TES roundtrip efficiency, the COP improvement reaches the maximum at approximately 15 %. The COP improvement steadily decreases as TES roundtrip efficiency drops, reaching 0 % when TES efficiency is at 0 %. At this point, the FlexiCO₂-HP performs similarly to the standard single-stage heat pump, highlighting the critical role that the TES efficiency plays in boosting system's COP. It is therefore critical to optimise the thermal energy storage system to achieve the potential of the FlexiCO₂-HP.

4. Conclusion

This paper proposes and demonstrates a *trans*-critical flexible heat pump cycle using CO₂ as a refrigerant (FlexiCO₂-HP). It can increase the average COP of *trans*-critical CO₂ heat pumps at different gas cooler pressures. These findings highlight the potential of the flexible heat

pump cycle concept to improve the energy efficiency of CO₂ heat pump systems.

The results revealed that the FlexiCO₂-HP cycle improves COP by around 10 % and 40 % over the standard single-stage *trans*-critical CO₂ cycle for the various gas cooler temperatures of 35–60 °C and different gas cooler pressures. Moreover, the analysis includes heat pump configurations that incorporate various expansion work recovery mechanisms, such as ejectors and expanders, alongside *trans*-critical two-stage CO₂ heat pump cycles. It was found that the FlexiCO₂-HP is thermodynamically similar to a two-stage *trans*-critical CO₂ cycle with full sub-cooling. Moreover, the results also show that the FlexiCO₂-HP can

Fig. 9. Compressor efficiency in CO₂ heat pump as a function of gas cooler pressure under *trans*-critical conditions.

Fig. 10. Comparison of COP between the CO₂ *trans*-critical heat pump with ejector and the FlexiCO₂-HP across varying gas cooler pressures, with the gas cooler temperature held constant at 50 °C. The COP values for heat pumps with ejector systems at efficiencies between 20 % and 40 % [32–34].

Table 1

Optimal intermediate temperature and gas-cooler pressure settings for various heat pump configurations.

Layout	SC&PIC	SC&FIC	FGR&FIC	FGR&PIC	FGR	SC	Flexible
T_{optimal} (°C)	23.3	18.9	17.2	21.8	21.6	23	23
P_{optimal} (MPa)	11.1	11.35	11.4	10.9	10.9	11.1	11.1

Fig. 11. COP comparison of heat pumps: The COP of the FlexiCO₂-HP is compared with that of a heat pump equipped with an expander system. The efficiencies (η_{ex}) considered between 28–55 % as reported in [35,36]. The comparison is conducted at a fixed gas cooler temperature of 50 °C and an evaporator temperature of 0 °C, across varying gas cooler pressures.

Fig. 12. COP improvement of the FlexiCO₂-HP at different TES efficiencies. The gas cooler temperature is set to 50 °C, gas cooler pressure to 11.1 MPa, compressor efficiency to 0.66 (for COP improvement graph), and TES temperature to 23 °C.

achieve a comparable COP to the heat pumps enhanced with expanders or ejectors.

The proposed FlexiCO₂-HP requires only one compressor, and thus are simpler and potentially cheaper than two-stage CO₂ systems which normally require two compressors or systems with expanders. However, it should be highlighted that the efficiency of the thermal energy storage has strong influence on the FlexiCO₂-HP's capability of COP improvement. It is therefore crucial to optimise the TES design, in terms of both thermal insulation and heat transfer, to maximise the potential of the FlexiCO₂-HP.

To fully demonstrate the potential of the proposed FlexiCO₂-HP, more advanced dynamic modelling, which considers all heat transfer, pressure losses, and compressors' efficiencies, will be required to analyse it under real operational conditions. Furthermore, prototypes should be developed to verify and demonstrate this new concept.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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